

soil, bundled in nylon net, and buried about 5 cm deep in the root zone. Sclerotia survival was recorded at 1 1/2, 2, and 2 1/2 mo after burial. After the specified burial period, sclerotia were retrieved from the bundles, sterilized in mercuric chloride, and put in petri dishes previously layered with potato dextrose agar fortified with streptomycin sulfate for recording germination.

The figure shows that although survival rate of the sclerotia did not vary markedly in the root zones of rice and weeds, it declined significantly in the root zone of dhaincha. In all the cases, survival rate was less after 2 1/2 mo than after 1 1/2 mo. It appears that the environment of dhaincha root reduces survival of the sclerotia of *R. solani*. However, dhaincha leaves became severely infected when artificially inoculated with the fungus. □

Percent survival of *R. solani* sclerotia in the root zone of different plants at different periods.

Influence of bacterial leaf streak (BLS) on bacterial blight (BB) of rice

A. Premalatha Dath and S. Devadath, Division of Plant Pathology, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, Orissa, India

BB (caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*) and BLS (caused by *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola*) are the most important bacterial diseases of rice in India. In the rainy months of Jul-Sep, both diseases affect rice over a substantial area. Rainy weather favors disease dissemination and infection. The bacterial

ooze from the leaves under high humidity is spread by wind-driven rains and by leaf contact.

We studied the interaction of the diseases on leaves of AC360, a cultivar highly susceptible to both diseases.

Leaves were inoculated with BLS by rubbing, then 2 d later were inoculated with BB by clipping. Disease development was assessed 5-7 d later. The progressive end of the BB lesion failed to develop water-soaking and it progressed slowly with orange discoloration, indicating almost a masking effect of BLS on BB development.

When leaves were first inoculated with

BB and inoculated with BLS 4 d later, disease assessment at 3 d showed BLS lesions developed more slowly than when leaves were inoculated first with BLS. Lesions turned brown and produced less bacterial ooze than did the rapidly elongating water-soaked lesions with abundant bacterial ooze that developed far from the BB lesion and also on leaves with only BLS infection. In screening rices for resistance to BB and BLS, caution needs to be exercised in rating their reaction if the plants are infected with both pathogens. □

Purification and serology of rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV)

H. Hibino and P. Q. Cabauatan, Plant Pathology Department, IRRI

We used the procedure followed for rice waika virus (RWV) in Japan to purify RTSV. RTSV-infected TNI plants (without roots) were homogenized in 0.01 M ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), pH 8.0. The sap was clarified by heating at 40°C for 1 h and the virus was precipitated with 7% polyethylene

glycol 6,000, 0.2 M sodium chloride, and 1% triton X-100.

The resuspended virus was treated with 20% carbon tetrachloride and subjected to different centrifugation (40,000 rpm for 40 min, then 10,000 rpm for 10 min, at 4°C in a Beckman RT-65 rotor). Supernatant was layered on 10-50% linear sucrose density gradient (prepared in 0.01 M phosphate buffer [PB], pH 7.4), and centrifuged at 25,000 rpm for 180 min at 4°C in a Beckman SW 27 rotor.

The light scattering band (virus zone,

about 3 cm from the meniscus) was collected, diluted with 0.01 M EDTA (pH 8.0), and centrifuged at 40,000 rpm for 40 min. The virus was resuspended in 0.01 M PB (pH 7.4) and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 min. The resulting supernatant contained isometric particles about 30 nm in diameter very similar to RWV (Fig. 1). Purified preparations had maximum ultraviolet (UV)-light absorption at 259-260 nm and minimum at 239-240 nm. The UV absorption ratio at 260 nm and 280 nm (A_{260}/A_{280}) for purified virus ranged from 1.52 to 1.74.

Rabbits were immunized against RTSV by 4 intramuscular and 1 intraveinal injections at 2-wk intervals with purified virus (A_{260} adjusted to 1.0 mixed with equal volume of Freund's complete adjuvant). An antiserum with a titer of 1:640 in ring interface precipitin and 1:160 in double gel diffusion (Ouchterlony) tests was obtained. An Ouchterlony test was used to compare RTSV and RWV antisera. A single band formed between homologous and heterologous combinations and the reaction bands fused (Fig. 2). Hence, RTSV is not only morphologically similar but also serologically identical to RWV. □

1. Electron micrograph of purified RTSV negatively stained with 2% phosphotungstic acid (200,000X), IRRI.

2. Ouchterlony test showing serological relation between RTSV and RWV: the center well contains purified RTSV and outer wells contain antiserum to RWV (W), antiserum to RTSV (S), and phosphate buffer (b), IRRI.

An alternative host for *Ustilaginoidea virens* (Cke.) Tak.

S. A. Shetty and H. S. Shetty, *Applied Botany Department, University of Mysore 570006, India*

Rice false smut, also known as pseudosmut or green smut, caused by *Ustilaginoidea virens* (Cke.) Tak. was first reported by Cooke (1878) from Tinnevely in Tamil Nadu, India. The disease cycle of the pathogen is still obscure.

During an extensive survey of false smut incidence in Dakshina Kannada District in 1983 kharif, we found that

Digitaria marginata L., a common rice weed, also was infected with false smut in 85% of the fields surveyed.

We conducted a cross-inoculation test to determine the infectivity to rice panicles of smut spores occurring on *D. marginata*. Smut balls (pseudomorphs) were collected from infected *D. marginata* and a spore suspension (about 10^4 spores/ml) was prepared in sterile distilled water. The suspension was inoculated on individual Basmati spikelets. The inoculated panicles were covered with polyethylene bags for 15 d and observed for smut ball development.

Ten days after inoculation, yellowish

smut balls began to emerge from the glumes. About half of the inoculated florets developed into smut balls.

We found *D. marginata* around the field was infected with false smut before panicle-bearing rice tillers matured. It is possible that when rice flowers open, the smut spores from infected *D. marginata* become airborne and infect them. Either chlamyospores from hibernating pseudomorphs or ascospores from germinated sclerotia may act as primary inoculum for infecting *D. marginata*. From *D. marginata* the smut spores cross-infect rice. □

Rice yellow dwarf in Tamil Nadu, India

G. Arjunan, R. Samiyappan, V. Mariappan, A. V. R. Reddy, and R. Jeyarajan, *Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India*

Yellow dwarf infected a large area of rice in Pudukkottai District of Tamil Nadu in Aug 1984. Of 1,000 ha surveyed, more than 200 ha in rice at different growth stages was affected. In each infected field, 1 m² was randomly selected, total and infected hills were counted, and percent disease was calculated. ADT36, TKM9, IR20, and IR50 were susceptible (see table). Maximum infection was 40% on IR20. Co 33 had 7% infection. Green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* popula-

Incidence of yellow dwarf in rice varieties, Tamil Nadu, India.

Village surveyed	Variety	Infection (%)
Satharam	ADT36	12.6
Kamathipuram	ADT36	24.1
Arimalam	ADT36	10.0
Kamarajapuram	ADT36	18.8
Mirattunilai	ADT36	16.6
Mirattunilai	ADT36	12.5
	IR20	39.6
	IR20	21.8
	IR20	14.2
	IR20	23.1
	IR20	19.8
Meenakshipuram	TKM9	15.9
Mirattunilai	IR50	10.0
Kalyanapuram	Co 33	1.5

tion was high. Although some disease had been noticed in previous years, this was the first widespread occurrence. □

Development of rice ragged stunt virus (RSV) in the vector brown planthopper (BPH)

A. Parejarearn and H. Hibino, *IRRI*

We studied RSV development in BPH. Virus-free BPH 1st and 3d-instar nymphs were allowed to feed separately on RSV-infected plants for 4 d and then held on healthy TN1 seedlings. Insects were collected every 2 d and homogenized with 0.2 M phosphate buffered-saline (pH 6.5) containing 0.05% Tween plus 2% polyvinylpyrrolidone at 0.05 ml/insect and 0.1 ml/insect for 1st and 3d instars. Extracts were tested for RSV antigen in ELISA using polystyrene microtitre plates (immulon). The relative content